

Details of Dataset Used for Code Smell Detection Study

Description:

The datasets used in this study were derived from the Qualitas Corpus, a collection of open-source Java systems for empirical software engineering research. They were constructed using object-oriented metrics extracted with the Design Features and Metrics for Java (DFMC4) tool. Six targeted code smell classes were analyzed: Large Class, Long Method, God Class, Long Parameter List, Switch Statements, and Data Class.

Data Source and Access:

The original software systems were obtained from the Qualitas Corpus. They can be accessed at: <https://qualitascorpus.com/download/>.